

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Using the Embedded Registration User Interface

How to register tissue blocks into 3D reference organs using the Registration User Interface within a data ingest portal

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Introduction

The Human Reference Atlas (<https://humanatlas.io>) integrates healthy human tissue blocks from a variety of curated sources into 3D reference organs. This SOP is written for consortium members who would like to upload tissue data via ingest portals such as the HuBMAP Ingest Portal (<https://ingest.hubmapconsortium.org>) or the SenNet Ingest Portal (<https://data.sennetconsortium.org>). The document contains instructions for spatially registering human tissue blocks to a 3D reference organ using the Registration User Interface (RUI). The primary goal is to facilitate an accurate and efficient registration process. The latest video demonstration of this process can be found at https://youtu.be/j4f9_xdBrK0.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **RUI Support Personnel** are the MC-IU contacts at Indiana University who assist users with tissue registrations.

The **Tissue Data Provider** is the person utilizing the RUI to register tissue blocks.

Role	Name	Email
RUI Support Personnel	Andreas Bueckle Danial Qaurooni	abueckle@iu.edu , dequeue@iu.edu
Tissue Data Provider	various	various

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

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Procedures

Registering a new sample and getting an extraction site

The embedded RUI is typically accessible via the tissue sample registration page.

Metadata such as author name, date, etc. is captured as part of the tissue ingest process and RUI data is automatically associated with the tissue block on Globus. Use the HuBMAP EUI (<https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/ccf-eui>) or the SenNet EUI (<https://data.sennetconsortium.org/ccf-eui>) to check data accuracy. In the procedural steps below, we use the HuBMAP Ingest portal as an example. Note that if the sample for which you register an extraction site is unpublished, you need to be logged into your portal to see it in the EUI.

- For HuBMAP visit <https://ingest.hubmapconsortium.org>
- For SenNet, visit <https://data.sennetconsortium.org>.
 - For more information about submitting data to the SenNet portal, refer to the Data Submission Guideline at <https://docs.sennetconsortium.org/data-submission/>.
- If needed, log in using your institutional credentials.

- Click the Sample tab on the top to see existing samples or to register a new sample.

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INDIVIDUAL BULK UPLOAD SAMPLE METADATA DATA INGEST BOARD abueckle@iu.edu EDIT PROFILE LOG OUT

Donor
Sample
Dataset
Publication

Please prepare any submissions using the new next-generation metadata and directory schemas, which are linked from [this page](#). The schemas you should use "use this one" on the schema pages. You can validate next-gen metadata schemas using the [process outlined here](#). Please also update [check spreadsheet](#) so we know what data is coming from your team. We're looking forward to your submissions! Please contact [help@artium.org](#) if you have questions.

Search

Use the filter controls to search for Donors, Samples, Datasets, Data Uploads, Publications, or Collections.
If you know a specific ID you can enter it into the keyword field to locate individual entities.

Group: All Components Type: ---

Keywords:

Enter a keyword or HuBMAP/Submission/Lab ID; For wildcard searches use * e.g., VAN004*

SEARCH CLEAR

COLUMNS FILTERS DENSITY EXPORT

Created By	HubMAP ID	Submission ID	Lab ID	Type	Group Name
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- Click the Source ID text input field. This will prompt a search for a Source ID for your Sample.

Sample Information

Do not provide any Protected Health Information. This includes the 18 identifiers specified by HIPAA

Source ID *

Sample Category *

Preparation Protocol *

Generate IDs for multiple samples

- Click the Group dropdown menu and choose your component.

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- Click the Type dropdown menu and select Organ.

- Click Search.

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HubMAP

All Components Organ

Enter a keyword or HubMAP/Submission/Lab ID; For wildcard searches use * e.g., VAN004*

Search Clear

HubMAP ID	Submission ID	Lab ID	Type	Group Name	Created By
HBM324.BVRW.855			Data Upload		wdong@hms.harvard.edu
HBM848.NFKX.276			Data Upload		wdong@hms.harvard.edu
HRM668.QFDW.774			sc_atac_seq_snare	University of California San Diego	hubmap@hubmapcon
HBM235.BMKX.955			sc_atac_seq_snare	University of California San Diego ...	hubmap@hubmapcon

CLOSE

- A list of organs is displayed. Pick one by clicking its row.

HubMAP

Search for a Source ID for your Sample

Use the filter controls to search for Donors, Samples, Datasets or Data Uploads. If you know a specific ID you can enter it into the keyword field to locate individual entities.

Group Type

All Components Organ

Enter a keyword or HubMAP/Submission/Lab ID; For wildcard searches use * e.g., VAN004*

Search Clear

HubMAP ID	Submission ID	Lab ID	Type	Group Name	Created By
HBM464.TKHM.272	CALT		Spleen	California Institute of Technology ...	danaj77@uw.edu
HRM383.0GI.P.747	UCSD0037-RI	D20-Bladder	Bladder	University of California San Diego	aknoten@wustl.edu

CLOSE

protocols.io DOI

- This returns you to the Sample Information page, displaying the newly added Source ID. Click the Tissue Sample Type dropdown menu and select the appropriate entry, then fill out the other fields as needed. You can start the registration process by pressing the blue Register Location button.

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HUBMAP REGISTER NEW: INDIVIDUAL + BULK + abueckle@tu.edu EDIT PROFILE LOGOUT

Sample Information

Do not provide any Protected Health Information. This includes the 16 identifiers specified by HIPAA

Source ID ⓘ
HBM464.TKHM.272

Source Type: Organ
Organ Type: Spleen
Submission ID: CALT0015-SP
Group Name: California Institute of Technology TMC

Tissue Sample Type ⓘ
Fresh frozen tissue

Preparation Protocol ⓘ ⓘ
protocols.io DOI

Generate IDs for multiple Fresh frozen tissue samples

Lab Sample Id ⓘ
Lab specific Alpha-numeric id

Sample Location ⓘ
Register Location

Description ⓘ

- The RUI is displayed, embedded into the page, with the organ of your choice as well as organ laterality and the donor sex selected based on the organ.
- Follow the steps outlined in the Place Tissue section.
- When done, click the Generate ID button in the Ingest Portal.

Tissue Sample type ⓘ
Fresh frozen tissue

Preparation Protocol ⓘ ⓘ
protocols.io DOI

Generate IDs for multiple Fresh frozen tissue samples

Lab Sample Id ⓘ
Lab specific Alpha-numeric id

Sample Location ⓘ
Register Location
View Location

Description ⓘ

Sample Metadata Status
No value set

Add a Metadata File

Add an Image file

Upload de-identified images only

Generate ID Cancel

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Adding an extraction site to an existing sample

If you have already registered your sample and need to add the extraction site via the RUI, you can follow the steps below.

Note: This only works if the sample is unpublished.

- Proceed as if you are registering a new sample.
- Instead of selecting Organ, select Sample, and click Search. You will then see a listing of all the registered samples for the selected team.
 - You can also enter a HuBMAP ID to find the sample in question.
- Select the tissue for which you would like to register an extraction site. Click the Register Location button.

Creating an extraction site in the RUI

Prepare for registration

- The RUI currently supports 65 organs as of September 2024. Check whether the RUI supports your organ by visiting the latest HRA organ library available at: <https://humanatlas.io/3d-reference-library>.
- Gather any materials needed to document where the tissue block was extracted from. At a minimum, this includes donor sex and age bracket and the approximate tissue block size. Additional information such as precise age, Body-Mass Index (BMI), and tissue orientation are highly valuable. If you are missing metadata needed for spatial registration, please refer to the Tissue Registration Issues section below. Except in rare circumstances, we encourage you to proceed with registration and document the missing information.
- Open the embedded RUI interface.

Place tissue

If this is your first time using the RUI, please read through the Description of the User Interface (UI) section, which is included as an appendix to this document.

- Resize the tissue block using the Tissue Block Dimensions text input fields in the top right corner. The default is a 10x10x10 mm block.
- Enter tissue section thickness in micrometers.
- Move the tissue block into position.
- When using the mouse, the tissue block can only be moved in two dimensions at a time.
 - To make “looking inside” the reference organ easier, all anatomical structures are set to 20% opacity as the default. You can adjust the opacity of all or individual anatomical structures using the opacity slider in the top-left pane of the RUI.
 - To inspect tissue blocks you placed before (for reference), click the Previously Registered Blocks toggle button in the metadata pane on the left. Clicking this toggle button will show all previously registered tissue blocks based on your browser’s local cache. This feature is supported on all major browsers.

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- To change the perspective, use the radio buttons in the 3D pane.
- To verify the placement, switch to 3D Preview mode using the corresponding toggle switch at the top of the 3D pane.
- At any time, the tissue block can be moved by pressing the W, A, S, D, Q, or E keyboard buttons, see **Fig. 2**. Each button moves the tissue block by 0.5 mm either into the positive or negative direction of an axis. The WASDQE buttons can be used at any time, regardless of whether the application is in Register or 3D Preview mode.

Figure 2: The WASDQE buttons move the tissue block along individual axes.

- Adjust the rotation of the tissue block by using the rotation sliders in the manipulation pane on the right.

Review and download registration data

- Once you have finished registering, click the Review and Download button.
- A Registration Review window pops up so you can check the validity of the data you generated.
- The RUI window will then close automatically and you will be redirected to the portal

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Figure 3: The Exploration User Interface (EUI)

Figure 4: One tissue block with 26 tissue sections and their associated datasets, here CellDive and a publication.

Validating registrations before final submission

It is important to double-check the registration before final submission. The validation procedure involves confirming the accuracy of tissue block location, size, and orientation, the associated anatomical structure tags, as well as demographic and technology information in the HuBMAP EUI (<https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/ccf-eui>) or the SenNet EUI (<https://data.sennetconsortium.org/ccf-eui>). Depending on portal architecture and backend processing steps, it might take anywhere between a few minutes and a full day before your data

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appears in the relevant EUI. We therefore recommend completing validation in a separate session/day from the previous procedures.

The validation process is as follows:

- Navigate to the appropriate EUI, whether HuBMAP (<https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/ccf-eui>) or SenNet (<https://data.sennetconsortium.org/ccf-eui>)
- After making sure you are logged in, use the top-center organ carousel and the top-left filters to isolate your tissue block(s).
- Check the information associated with each tissue block for accuracy. Here are some items to consider for review:
 - Anatomical structure tags
 - Demographic information, such as sex, age, and BMI
 - Tissue block information, including the 3D size, position, and rotation of the tissue blocks. If tissue blocks were cut into sections, make sure to verify their number, thickness, and sequence using the listing on the right hand side (see **Fig. 4**)
 - Technology information, including spatial assay types (e.g., CODEX) or suspension based assay types (e.g., scRNAseq analysis). Make sure all data is available for each tissue section or suspension on the right hand side.

A validation example is detailed in this video: <https://youtu.be/UloDIG0S64w>

Reusing an existing extraction site

- To modify and/or reuse an existing extraction site, you need to have the relevant JSON file ready. After opening the RUI, go to the window (**Fig. 1**), select Upload, and navigate to the folder where the JSON is located. Alternatively, you can use the Upload button in the right pane of the RUI to upload a previously saved JSON.
- Make any adjustments to the location and metadata of the extraction site.
- Once completed, click the Review and Download button in the bottom right corner of the screen to review the data and download it as a JSON file.

Tissue Registration Issues

In a number of situations, the user might have doubts about whether the tissue sample can or should be spatially registered. For example, the tissue might be missing some metadata or there might be a size or shape difference between the organ from which the tissue was extracted and the 3D reference organ. With a few exceptions, the general guidance in such cases is to proceed with the registration process while documenting the issue. In case your tissue sample is missing metadata or there is another issue that you would like to report, please use this form:

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<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSe0falih0S-1zqn5FCdaICF7YTxBK7ECMgg0svVv0dyIEF7gKQ/viewform>. Based on your report, you will either be granted an exemption from registration or asked to document the issue and proceed.

Best Practices

Below is a list of best practices to ensure that the spatial registration process goes smoothly and errors are minimized:

Complete spatial registration when tissues are sectioned

Prioritize conducting spatial registrations directly after sectioning tissue samples whenever possible. This approach helps preserve the accuracy of spatial information and minimizes morphological alterations that might occur over time.

Document the extraction site in detail

In scenarios where immediate spatial registration is impractical, carefully document the extraction site. Photographs and detailed annotations on anatomical images can help accurately capture the original 3D size, location, and orientation of the tissue. Such documentation aids subsequent tissue extraction and registration efforts.

Preserve context

- For diseased tissue, clinical imaging, surgeon's operative notes (if available), and pathology notes can provide insights into the specific characteristics and conditions of the tissue.
- For normal tissue, communication between the surgeon, the tissue collector, and the specimen collection manager can improve documentation accuracy and handling of tissue samples.

Use anatomical landmarks to align tissue

The Anatomical Landmarks pane on the bottom left side of the RUI interface serves as a useful reference for orienting tissue samples and navigating reference organs.

Train multiple team members to use the RUI

Ensure that multiple team members are trained in using the RUI to prevent processing bottlenecks. Having several proficient RUI users allows for continuity in work, even in the absence of key personnel.

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References and Resources

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- HRA Portal: <https://humanatlas.io>. Accessed on May 23, 2024.
- Validation demo: <https://youtu.be/UloDIG0S64w>. Accessed on Nov 13, 2024.

Glossary

Cellular Senescence Network (SenNet): The Cellular Senescence Network Program was established and funded by the Common Fund at the National Institutes of Health to comprehensively identify and characterize the differences in aging cells across the body, across various states of human health, and across the lifespan. SenNet will provide publicly accessible atlases of senescence using data collected from multiple human and model organism tissues.

Globus: Globus is software-as-a-service for research data management, used by hundreds of research institutions and High Performance Computing (HPC) facilities worldwide for secure, reliable file transfer, sharing and publication.

HuBMAP: The Human BioMolecular Atlas Program is a consortium composed of diverse research teams funded by the Common Fund at the National Institutes of Health. HuBMAP is developing the tools to create an open, global atlas of the human body at the cellular level. These tools and maps will be used to accelerate understanding of the relationships between cell and tissue organization and function and human health.

HuBMAP Ingest Portal: The HuBMAP Ingest Portal is where HuBMAP members generate HuBMAP IDs.

Mapping Component-Indiana University (MC-IU): The Indiana University team is one of two teams in the HuBMAP consortium tasked with building an atlas of tissue maps. These two teams are identified as mapping components, as opposed to components or teams that develop tools or provide infrastructure support.

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Reference Organ: A reference organ is a 3D model based on a variety of potential data sources produced by MC-IU. Subject matter experts are involved with the creation of 3D models.

Registration User Interface (RUI): Registration user interface developed by MC-IU, available via HuBMAP Data Ingest Portal and <https://apps.humanatlas.io/rui>.

Tissue Block: A tissue block is a digital, 3D representation of a tissue sample. In the RUI, tissue blocks are cuboids that one can spatially register to a reference organ.

Tissue Section: A tissue section is a slice of a tissue block. Tissue sections inherit the location and rotation of their parent tissue block. The thickness and number of tissue sections is captured with an input field inside the RUI.

Tissue Suspension: A tissue prepared for bulk analysis.

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Appendix: Description of the Registration User Interface (RUI)

The RUI currently supports tissue registration for the organs listed in the [3D Reference Object Library](#).

Figure 1: The stand-alone RUI. The yellow cuboid represents the tissue block. The green slide indicates the bisection line inside the kidney.

The RUI layout consists of three panes (**Fig. 2**): the **structures and landmarks** pane on the left, the **3D** pane in the middle, and the **metadata and manipulation** pane on the right.

Figure 2: The RUI has three panes: anatomical structures and landmarks (left with pink outline), 3D view (middle in yellow), and tissue block metadata and manipulation (right in blue).

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The following is a brief description of the actions each pane makes possible.

- The left pane contains the following elements:
 - a. **Anatomical Structures** lists the 3D structures inside the selected reference organ. A slider appears when you hover over the drop icon to the left of the anatomical structure text entry, making it possible to adjust the opacity of the structure. This allows making certain parts of the organ more transparent than others and retaining certain structures as landmarks while omitting others to facilitate tissue placement. Clicking the eye icon to the right of the slider will hide the structure.
 - b. **Landmarks** lists visual cues that allow you to recognize the anatomy of the organ (such as the bisection line for the kidney). All landmarks are hidden by default and if made visible are rendered in green.
- The **3D pane** in the middle contains the reference organ and the tissue block. It is a 3D window, similar to what one would find in 3D modeling software or a video game. In the top left corner, a set of radio buttons allow you to control the 3D camera of the scene.
 - a. Using the radio buttons labeled Left, Right, Anterior, and Posterior, you can rotate the camera around the reference organ in increments of 90 degrees. The current camera view is visually indicated by a small human icon on the right side of the 3D pane.
 - b. When Left, Right, Anterior, or Posterior are clicked, the camera movement is restricted to 90 degree increments, and the mouse is used to move the tissue block. Select 3D Preview to verify tissue placement. When in 3D Preview mode, you can rotate the camera at two degrees of freedom while clicking and dragging the left mouse button. You can also zoom in by using the mouse scroll wheel (or whatever input method is assigned to scrolling) and pan the camera (i.e., move it laterally) by clicking and dragging the right mouse button.

Figure 3: The z-axis should correspond to the cutting direction of the tissue block.

- c. In the top right corner, the current x, y, z-coordinates of the tissue block are shown, with the origin in the back bottom left corner of the reference organ.

